

DR.GIRIJA SESHAMAMBA's SERVICES AND CONTRIBUTIONS TO INDIAN CLASSICAL MUSIC

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ABSTRACT : Dr. Potharaju Girija Seshamamba is a child prodigy in Carnatic Music. She bagged two world records in her career. Dr.Girija's 45 years of experienced in her Carnatic Music. She achieved many Records, Awards including social service works, service oriented programs through her music. Dr.Girija Seshamamba is a Versatile artist and a good human being. She conducted many workshops and webinars in different modes and new teaching methods. Dr. Girija ia not only a good artist and performer she is a good teacher and guru also. Her teaching methods and techniques are very unique and easy to understand by students. She is a best teacher awardee also. She trained music to many students. She is a such a great women such as multiple aspects. This paper is intended to introduced Dr.P. Girija Seshamamba musical journey and to highlight her achievements. Her knowledge in Carnatic classical music is definitely useful to the aspirants of Carnatic music world.

KEY WORDS: Music, Carnatic Music, Thyagaraja Kritis, Conserts, South Indian Music. Composers.

INTRODUCTION: Indian culture is a rich and diverse heritage that is influenced by a history that goes back thousands of years. Indian classical music is a rich tradition that originated in south Asia. The music of south India is known as Carnatic music. It is a classical music tradition which originated from the origin of Vedas. It was influenced by scholars, saints and composers. In Carnatic music great musicians and Vaggeyakaras and also many famous composers are in south India. Saint Tyagaraja was a great composer and one of the Sangeeta Ratnatrayam of Carnatic music. In this Parampara or Streak or tradition Vidwan late Sri Parupalli Ramakrishnayya Panthulu garu is one of the Parampara of saint Tyagaraja. In this next generation Padmabhushan Mahamahopadhyaya dr. Nookala China Satyanarayana garu and Padmabhushan Dr. Mangalampalli Balamurali Krishna garu prominent musicians in Carnatic

music. The Parupalli Ramakrishnayya Panthulu garu his disciple late Smt. Thadepalli Sithamahalakshmi garu and her disciple Dr.P. Girija Seshamamba garu is a wellknown Classical Musician and Vidwan. Dr.P. Girija Seshamamba is a Performer, Teacher, Composer and Guru also.

Dr. Girija Seshamamba hails from a family with musical interest but not musical background and born to Sri Late. Potha Raju Kutumba Rao and Late. Smt.Lakshmi Hema Latha Devi in Machilipatnam. She started learning at the age of 3 and half years, 15 Rupees fees per month. Her father Late. Sri Pothu Raju Kutumba Rao took her to Late Smt. Thadepalli Seetha Maha Lakshmi garu from Machilipatnam, a Disciple of Late. Sri Parupalli Ramakrishnayya Panthulu . That's how She entered in to the Lineage of Sri Parupalli Ramakrishnayya Pantulu. Sri Panthulu was a direct descendant of the sisya parampara of Saint Thyagaraja. May be beacuse of that Lineage she was drawn towards Tyagaraja as base for her Reasearch work. Her first performance was at the age of 7 at Edepalli Anjaneya swamy temple, Machilipatnam, Andhra Pradesh. Soon after, Girija began learning with her Guru Smt. Thadepalli Seetha Maha Lakshmi garu who added great values of tradition, discipline and ethics in her music and personality through intense teaching and training from a very early age. Her experience with guru was like a mother and child not like student and teacher. Her guru was very affectionate and shaped 100's of students in music and dedicated her life to music. She was very much inspired by her guru and always feel gratitude towards her guru for her position in music world. Dr. Girija began performing at the age of 7 and won several awards and accolades along her career. Dr. Girija was soon one of the youngest artistes in Carnatic Classical and Light Music to perform and given lectures in All India Radio at early ages. She also passed Certificate Course with the guidance of her Guru in very early age. She has been blessed to perform along with her guru accompanying on violin.

Since childhood she gave many performances on stage and people recognized her as a child prodigy. From childhood her father was her role model as he encouraged her in all aspects and with her parents support she continued her music from very early age. During her musical journey she was trained and guided by many gurus like Dr. Mythili garu, Smt. P.K. Indrani garu in B. Music and Dr Dwaram Lakshmi garu in M.A., (Music).Though she selected B. Music to bag a degree her passion and interest towards music keep on increasing and then she Completed

her M.A., Degree in Music as University Topper and bagged a Gold Medal in her career. While pursuing her Masters Degree her passion for Music and Bhakti towards Sangeetha Thrayam increased. Her deep intensity for music lead her to Ph.D., in Music and completed her thesis on “Apoorva Ragas of Thyagaraja’s Compositions” under the guidance of Dr Prapancham Sitaram garu in Sri Padmavathi Mahila Viswa vidyalayam, Tirupati. She learnt few Apoorva ragas from Dr. Nookala China Satyanarayana garu. She was trained Annamacharya Sankeerthanas under Sri Garimella Bala Krishna Prasad garu.

She was praised by her gurus stating that the way of presentation of Ragam, Tanam, Pallavi are really inspired and admirable of her workaholic nature and commitment. She obediently says that all the techniques are the prasadam of her gurus, for which she is grateful to all her gurus. During this travel she was motivated and inspired in different aspects in each guru and quickly imbibed in her with those qualities with passion, keen observation and rigorous hard work.

In this journey of life she got married to Dr. TATA Durga Vara Prasad, Senior Manager in Bank of India. Since then with his encouragement she never turned back and achieved many with his support. She gave number of performances, conducted many work shops, she has written and composed many songs and taught Carnatic Music to many. Always she says “It’s because of my gurus and my husband am here now”.

Her eidetic memory, keen observation and enormous hard work made her stand with two world records.

*By presenting Thyagaraja Swami Kritis (THYAGARAJA SWARARCHANA) for 12 hours Non-Stop performance from 9 AM to 9.15 pm – nominated her name in LIMCA BOOK OF WORLD RECORDS

*By presenting Thyagaraja Swami Kritis (THYAGARAJA SWARARCHANA 2) 14 hours Non-Stop performance from 7.30 AM to 9.30 PM – nominated her name in INDIA BOOK OF RECORDS

In contrast to this single artiste project, Girija is the founder of Sree Sesha Sai Sangeetha Academy -through which she conducted many workshops and taught patriotic songs to many street children and rag pickers of Jan Vikas Society, Mumbai.

She visited orphan homes in Panvel and Kopherkairne and conducted free workshop and taught them patriotic songs. She prepared them for a performance on 26th Jan 2010. This touching act of spreading the knowledge of divine music showed her enthusiasm to inculcate patriotism in the deserted children. Prior to this project she has taken up many projects to teach patriotic songs to the municipal school children. She also taught songs in different languages to 1500 school children and had a grand program on 26th Jan 2008 along with 1500 school children in Mumbai, which was inspired by many teachers in Mumbai.

Her another notable project with her service oriented nature made her to conduct a workshop for women prisoners in Chanchalguda Jail, Hyderabad by teaching them patriotic songs which is an act of humanity towards people and nation. Apart from that she conducted many workshops for women so they can put that seed of interest towards carnatic music on their children and grandchildren.

A program of her in the name of SIVAPADAM the songs of Sri Samavedam Shanmukha Sarma garu composed and sung by Dr Girija garu and the explanation by Sri Samavedam Shanmukha Sarma garu at Mumbai was a memorable program to Mumbai Telugu people.

Besides music she is a Kuchipudi dancer and holds a certificate from kalakshethra and also a Veena and Violin player too. Versatile Girija Seshamamba has taken Music as her career and bagged many achievements and awards from various reputed organizations. To say few:

- Two World Records (Limca Book of World Reords and India Book of Records)
- Doctorate
- Gold medal
- Apoorva Raga Gana Kokila
- Sangeetha Sri

- Sangeetha Saraswathi
- Karnataka Sangeetha Kausthubham
- Dasabda Mahila
- Andhra Ratnam
- State Best Citizen
- Best Teacher Award by INSC-Benguluru-2021
- Best Teacher Award by Bharath Vikas Parishat- Hyderabad, 2022
- Rabindranath Tagore Kalavibhushan-2023

In addition to above she was also honoured as Asthana Vidushimani for “Trisakthi Durga Peetham” Sattenapalle, Guntur District and Kodanda Ramaswamy Temple, Kanchipeetham at Hyderabad “Siva Rama Kshethram”. She composed and recorded an album called “Bhakthi Mala” and CD was released in which 108 songs were written and composed by DR. Girija and gave opportunity to her her student to sing in that project.

DR. Girija has released CD’s on

- Thyagaraja Apoorva Ragas (compositions on Apoorva Ragas of Thyagaraja)
- Vividha Vaggeyakara Lahari (Krithis of different composers).

SANGEETA SWARA PRAKASIKA BOOK:

DR.Girija wrote and released book on Carnatic music – name sangeeta swara prakasika

With a performing career of more than 40 years, Dr. Girija Seshamamba –performer, writer, composer and Guru has evolved her own identity and style and has made Music as medium for her expression. She also completed L.L.B and training many interested aspirants and showing world that with music you can achieve anything. She is now aiming to to inculcate the habit of learning music and pass it on to the next generations, she is creating and taking more

opportunities to spread carnatic music, such as taking free classes through Sri Sesha Sai Sangeetha Academy by conducting free work shops.

All music listeners and Gurus proudly say that Dr. Girija Seshamamba is only the person who has bagged Two World Records in the category of Carnatic classical vocal by presenting exclusively Tyagaraja Kritis.

Concerts:

CONCERTS 1980-2000

- At Machilipatnam: 20.01.1987, 22.01.1988, 23.01.1989, 13.01.1990, 29.01.1990.
- At Vijayawada : 23.08.1990. At Visakhapatnam: 23.12.2009 & 24.12.2009.
- Programmes held on the eve of Sri Vari Bramhotsavams & on other occasions at Tirumala / Tirupati and nearby places of Tirupati:
- At Tirumala / Tirupati: 07.04.2001, 01.10.2006, 20.10.2007, 06.08.2000, 31.03.1996, 16.09.1992.
- At Tiruchanur: 29.10.2000, 15.10.2001, 02.04.2001. At Karvetinagar: 20.05.2001

CONCERTS :2000-2010

- Concert at S.V.Music College, Tirupati on 08.01.2010.
- Program at Nerul Bhakta Samaj, Nerul, Mumbai on 17.01.2010.
- Veena concert given at SIES, Nerul on 16.03.2010.
- Composition of songs and given performance – songs from Sivapadam on 11.01.2009 at Mumbai.
- Concert at Andhra Mahasabha on 28.04.2009.
- Program alongwith 60 women at Andhra Maha Sabha on 11.06.2009.

- Program on Annamacharya Keerthanas at Vashi, Mumbai 16.08.2009.
- Concert Worli, Mumbai on 19.09.2009.
- Concert at Matunga, Mumbai on 27.09.2009.
- Concert at Andhra Mahasabha, Mumbai on 13.04.2008.
- Concert at Madipakkam, Chennai on 16.11.2008.
- Program at Annamayya Kalavedika, Guntur on 12.02.2007.
- Concert at Andhra Mahasabha, Mumbai on the eve of Amurthotsavam functions on 28.10.2007.
- Concert at Vashi Fine Arts Academy, Mumbai on 15.08.2007.
- Concert at Andhra Maha Sabha, Mumbai on 28.10.2007.
- Concert at Telugu Kala Samithi, Mumbai on 07.05.2006.
- Concert at Nerul, Mumbai on 26.02.2006.
- Program at Sri Shanmukhananda Sangeetha Vidyalaya on 26.03.2005 on Vaggeyakara day.
- Concert at SKPD Matunga, Mumbai on 17.10.2004.
- Concert at Telugu Kala Samithi, Mumbai on 11.04.2003.
- Concert at SKPD Matunga, Mumbai on 28.09.2003.

CONCERTS :2010-2024

- **Nadaneerajanam : 1.November 9th 2020 at Tirumala nadaneerajanam live program.**
- **June 18th 2022 at tirumal nadaneerajanam live concert**
- **January 11th 2023 at Tirumala nadaneera live concert.**

- **Unjal program on 20th august 2023 at tiruchanur, live program at tirumal on 21st 2023.**
- **Unjal live program at Tirumal on 21st 2024 , Tiruchanoor on 22nd at Tirupati.**
- **Annamacharya akhnda ganam at annamachara kalamandapam , Tirupati on 22nd January 2024.**
- .December 9th and December 10th 2019 Tirumala and Tiruchanoor unjal seva in Tirupati.
- .November 23rd 2019 Tiruchanoor Padmavati Ammavaru Brahmotsavalu concert.
- .October 31st 2019 Lecture demonstration on Tyagaraja keerthanalu in Ramakrishna mission Tirupati.
- August 6th 2019 Tummalagunta Venkateswara Swamy temple at Tirupati.
- May 12 th and 13 th 2019 Tirumala and Tiruchanoor Unjal at Tirupati.
- May 5th 2019 Syamasastri utsavalu concert at kanchipuram.
- Concert on march 8th 2019 at Ramakrishna Mission Ashram Tirupati.

Lecture demonstration on Annamayya sankeerthanalu at Machilipatnam on Feb14th 2019

- Concert on February 1st 2019 Iskon temple Tirupati.
- November 5th 2018 Siva Padam concert organized by Samavedam samskruthika samanvaya samithi.
- October 25th and 26 th 2018 Tiruchanur and Tirumala Sahasra Deepalankarana seva.
- June 23rd 2018 Lecture demo in Tyagaraja Gana sabha in Guntur.
- Tirumala sreevari sahasradeepalankarana seva-Mar23 rd- 2018
- Tiruppavai Pasuralu concert in satyannarayana swami temple hyd-March 2018
- Tiruchanoor unjal-march 22-2018

- Felicitation by Bvp-November-2017
- MS SubbaLakshmi centenary concert-jan 29 – 2017
- Gayatri mahila mandali Guntur-jan 23 – 2017
- Concert at Tyagaraja ganasabha-Jan -2016
- Concert, Bhadrachalam- Feb - 14 th 2016
- Tirumala sree vari unjal seva-April 3rd-2016
- Tiruchanoor sahasradeepalankarana-April 4th-2016
- Dharmapracharaparishat Tirumala Asthana mandapam-may -15 th-2016
- Swaramrutam in jaya jaya sankara tv-June -2016
- Tiruchanoor unjal-July --18th-2016
- Tirumala sreevari unjal-July-19th-2016
- Krishnapushkaralu special concert sreesailam-August 13th-2016
- Jaya jaya sankara sree krishnasthami special-August 22-2016
- Felicitation by Hari hara rudra veena-August 28 th-2016
- vignana samiti concert hyd-Dec 2015
- Concert at MUMBAI ANDHRA MAHASABHA DADAR on 28-09-2015
- Concert at NAVI MUMBAI VASHI on 27-09-2015
- Concert at South Zone Cultural Centre, Thanjavur conducted by Ministry of culture, Govt of India at Brihadeeshwara temple on 19-09-2015
- Concert at Tirupati Annamacharya Kala Mandapam on 19-08-2015
- Program at Bhadrachalam conducted on occasion of Godavari pushkaralu on 23-07-2015

- Program at Saroor Nagar Siva Rama Kshetram on Mar 21 2015
- Program conducted by "RUSHI PEETHAM" on 14th April 2015,Hyderabad.
- Program organized by VIJAYA NAGAR FINE ARTS on30-01-2015
- Program at Saroor nagar Ramalayam on 13.09.2014
- Program at BHEL,Hyderabad on Feb 08 2014
- Program conducted by SICA ANNAMAYYA SPECIAL on 24-08-2014
- Program at Shilparamam on 12-01-2014
- Concert at Nallagunta on occasion of Thyagaraja Festival on 23-01-2014
- Program in davanagere, karnataka on 10.07.2014
- Concert at Tirumala Brahmotsavam at Annamacharya mandapam on 12-10-2013
- Concert at Gnana Saraswathi temple,Hyderabad on the occasion of Dussera Festival on 08.10.2013.
- Program on Vignana Samithi Patnam Subhramanya Iyer special on 06-10-2013
- Program at Shilparamam,Hyderabad on 09.03.2013
- Program at Himayathnagar TTD on 23-03-2013
- Program for Rama Navami Celebrations,Guruvayoor on 17-04-2013.
- Program for Vinayaka chavithi celebrations at Malaysian township on 21-09-2012
- Program at Asthana mandapam Tirumala on 15.09.2012
- Concert at Trishakti Peetham, Sattenapalli on 05.08.2012.
- Concert at Tyagarayagana sabha, Hyderabad for Vamsi Arts on 20.06.2012
- Concert at Sri Rama Temple, Nallakunta, Hyderabad on 29.03.2012.

- Concert at Dhyandrapradesh, Kadthal, Hyderabad on 20.02.2012.
- Program at Sivananda Ashram, Secunderabad on 19.02.2012.
- Concert at Lord Siva Temple, Srisailam on 16.02.2012.
- Concert at Lord Balaji Temple, Worli, Mumbai on 04.02.2012.
- Concert at Bhadrachalam on 19.01.2012.
- Program at Hayat Nagar, Hyderabad on 28.06.2011.
- Program at TTD Kalyana Mandapam on 06.08.2011.
- Concert at Ashtalakshmi Temple, Hyderabad on 05.09.2011
- Concert at Kachiguda, Hyderabad for Bank of India on 10.09.2011.
- Concert at Ashtalakshmi Temple, Hyderabad on 03.10.2011
- Concert at Vignana Samithi, Anandnagar, Hyderabad on 15.01.2011
- Program at Hayatnagar, Hyderabad on 28.06.2011 as Sangeeta Dhyanam
- Program at Ashtalakshmi temple on 03.10.2011
- Program at Lord Balaji Temple, Himayatnagar, Hyderabad on 06.08.2011

PERFORMANCE ON TELEVISION

- S.V.Bhakti Channel /Janata Tv.
- Program in Sapthagiri channel Vinayaka Chavithi special
- Programs Recorded In Tirupati And Hyderabad For Carnatic Classical.
- Special Program On Ragas Given At Janata Tv/ Hyderabad. The Program Was Relayed Weekly Twice, On Number Of Episode. The name of the program - RAGALAHARI
- Prepared Students To Perform On Pooja Channel

- Special Program As Judge For Sai Bhajan Samrat Audition In Sri Sankara Channel
- Raga Vipanchi - 90 Episodes - A Unique and Rare Program on Carnatic Classical Ragas Presented in Cvr Om Spiritual Channel – Highlighted Her Knowledge And Presentation Appreciated by Many music lovers and music Gurus.
- Pancharatna Gosti with women in Tollywood channel

PERFORMANCE AT ALL INDIA RADIO as B Grade Artist

- LIGHT MUSIC – B GRADE at Cuddapah : 18.07.2000, 06.02.2002.
- LIGHT MUSIC – at Hyderabad: 06.07.2005, 22.07.2004, 22.07.2003.2024
- LIGHT MUSIC - at Tirupati: 10.12.2001, 18.11.1999, 07.05.1994.
- Classical at Anantapur: 05.05.1992, 06.09.1991.
- Classical at Tirupati: 13.09.1994, 19.08.1996. etc.

ACHIEVEMENTS

DR. Girija has notable major achievements in her name to mention few:

- Gold medal in M.A Music from Governor Rangararajan garu
- Ph.D., Doctorate taken from Shri Shinde garu
- Entered her name in LIMCA BOOK OF WORLD RECORDS by presenting Thyagaraja swami kritis (THYAGARAJA SWARARCHANA) for 12 hours non-stop performance.
- Entered her name in INDIA BOOK OF RECORDS – by presenting Thyagaraja swami kritis (THYAGARAJA SWARARCHANA 2) 14 hours non-stop performance.

DR. Girija Seshamamba has been honoured with many Titles, awards and felicitations from many organisations to say few are mentioned below:

TITLES:

- SANGEETASRI

- SANGEETA SARASWATHI
- KARNATAKA SANGEETHA KOUSTHUBHAM
- DASABDA MAHILA
- ANDHRA RATNAM
- STATE BEST CITIZEN
- APOORVA RAGA GANA KOKILA

HONOURS:

- AASTHANA VIDUSHIMANI OF TRISAKTHI PEETHAM
- GOURAVA KARNATAKA SASTHREEYA SANGEETHA VIDUSHIMANI OF SIVARAMA KSHETHRAM

FELICITATIONS:

- FELICITATION BY MUMBAI MAYOR
- FELICITATION BY TELUGU KALA SAMITHI
- FELICITATION BY LIONS CLUB
- FELICITATION BY ROTARY CLUB
- FELICITATION BY ARYA VYSYA SANGHAM

WORKSHOPS

Workshops Conducted by DR. Girija;s Academy.

Sangeetha Sri – Dr. Girija Seshamamba taught patriotic songs to many street children and rag pickers of Jan Vikas Society, Mumbai. She visited orphan homes in Panvel and Kopherkairne for more than a month and taught them patriotic songs. She prepared them for a performance on 26th Jan 2010. This touching act of spreading the knowledge of divine music showed her enthusiasm to inculcate patriotism in the deserted children. Earlier also she has taken few tasks to

teach patriotic songs to the municipal school children. She has also taught songs in different languages to 1500 school children and she had a grand program on 26th Jan 2008 along with 1500 school children in Mumbai.

To inculcate habit of learning music and to pass it to the next generations, she is taking opportunity to spread the knowledge of carnatic music, such as taking free classes through Sri Sessa Sai Sangeetha Academy in Mumbai and conducting work shops.

Workshop conducted at Nagpur from 23rd April to 02nd May 2010 and had given a program along with participants at Nagpur on 02.05.2010 which was applauded by many people. At the request of residents of Navi Mumbai from 06.05.2010 to 05.06.2010, she conducted another workshop at Mumbai.

Conducted a free 40-day workshop at Sivananda Ashram, Padmarao Nagar, Hyderabad and program organized on 19-02-2012

Her Kindness and service oriented nature could not stop her to teach music to women prisoners in Chanchalguda Jail in Hyderabad and made them perform on 2nd October 2013.

Free 40-day Workshop conducted on Padma Rao Nagar Balaji Temple and participants performed in temple on 09-02-2013 .

Sree Sessa Sai Academy conducted a 40-day free Workshop and performance given at Gnana Saraswathi temple, Hyderabad on 14-03-2013.

Workshop conducted for 40 days free in Orphanage Girls school and made all to participate in a program conducted on Aug 15th 2014 on occasion of Independence Day.

Conducted a 40 days workshop at Saroor Nagar for women of different ages and made all of them to give performance at Sivarama Kshetram on 13.09.2014

Conducted a workshop in Chaitanyapuri Ramalayam in hyderabad and made participants to perform on june 6th 2015

Conducted online workshop on July 12th 2020 Topic- Learning and practice techniques in Carnatic music

Online workshop Topic- Dhanwantari and Durga Suladi on Aug 2nd 2020

VISION OF ACADEMY

1. To Instill soulful music in next generations.
2. To contribute to music therapy.
3. To generate interest in Carnatic music for all age groups.
4. To bring prominence to Apoorva Ragas of Thyagaraja's compositions.
5. To inculcate patriotism in the school children and deserted children.

To inculcate patriotism in school children that too in municipal school children visited 10 municipal schools of different language schools such as Telugu Medium, Tamil Medium, Kannada Medium. Taught 10 patriotic songs of 10 different languages i.e., Telugu, Tamil, Marathi, Kannada, Hindi, to 1500 school children from 10 Schools. There was a big choir singing program by all 1500 school children on 26.01.2007 on the eve of Republic Day, as HINDOSTHAN HAMARA-1.

To inculcate patriotism in street children and ragpickers also, visited orphan homes of Janvikas Society at Panvel, Taloja and Kopharkairne in Mumbai and taught patriotic songs to them; had given a choir singing program on 26.01.2010 on the eve of Republic Day, as HINDOSTHAN HAMARA-2.

To seed patriotism in inmates of Jail, and visited Chanchalguda Jail (Women wing) at Hyderabad and taught patriotic songs to inmates and presented a program on 02.10.2013 in the jail, as HINDOSTHAN HAMARA-3.

To create patriotism in orphan girl children she has visited a orphan home at Priyadarshini Urban Residential School Hostel Children, Kachiguda, Hyderabad and taught them various patriotic songs to the children and made them to present a good program in the presence of dignitaries on 15-08-2014 as HINDOSTHAN HAMARA-4.

Not only patriotic songs she had handled various projects where in she had made to learn various Thyagaraja swamy, Annamayya, Ramadasa kritis to middle age women and presented choir singing programs alongwith a group of (not less than 50 women students) at Mumbai, Nagpur and at Hydereabad.

APPRECIATIONS BY WELL KNOW MUSICIANS TO DR. GIRIJA SESHAMAMBA

1. Mahamahopadhyaya Dr. Nookala China Satyannarayana garu one of Dr.Girija's guru. "Girijas voice very melodious. She is a lady with good-looking her performances in concerts like an authoritative knowledge in Swarakalpana. She is a good knowledge in Manodharma Sangeetam."
2. Dr. C Narayana Reddy garu famous writer : "Girija Seshamamba is a laksha, lakshana vidvamsuralu. She is a eminentin sahitam and sangeetam also."
3. Late Smt. Thadepalli Sita Mahalakshmi garu: Dr.Girija's guru says "Girija expert in Manodharma Sangeetam especially Ragalapana and Swarakalpana. She changed Ragaas immediatly with fraction of seconds and very good Teaching".
4. Dr.Sabari Girish garu , lecturer in Sri Venkateswara Music College ,Tirupati, he is one of Dr.Girija's gurus says "Sangeeta Lakshya, lakshan Vidushimani and I surprised she is doing so many things for Music. I am very happy and she is one of my disciple."
5. P.K.Indrani garu (Rtd.) Lecturer in Sri Venkateswara Music College,Tirupati, she says "I feel very proud you are my student. I am very happy you having good knowledge in Carnatic Music."
6. Sri. L.V. Gangadhara Sastry a renounced Bhagavatgeeta founder, Bhagavat gita foundation. Sastry garu says "Girija is a Sublime Carnatica Sastriya Vidvanmani, Gayanimani. She has good knowledge in Ragaas."
7. Samanyava Saraswati Sri Samavedam Shanmukha Sarma garu says about Dr.Girija "Girija has good knowledge in Swaram , Swrakalpana. She is good knowledge about Ragaas".
8. Late Sri Kalanadhabhatta. Krishnamurthy garu founder of Annamacharya Association, President of Andhra Mahasabha, Telugu Kala Samiti, Vashi,Mumbai says about her "Dr.Girija Seshamamba having good knowledge about all the aspects in Carnatic Music. She is a good singer."

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- Mahatma charms women prisoners-DECCAN CHRONICLE
- Mumbai singer eyes to record for 14-hours-HINDUSTHAN TIMES
- Blessed with a soulful voice, Girija Seshamamba -39s recital carried a good range-HINDU
- 700 mesmerized fans and few sips of water sustain this gritty singer for 12-hours-METRO
- Dr. Girija sings into record books 14-hour classical marathon by the Carnatic vocalist ups her own record-NEWS BAND
- The Nerul 39s residents 12-hour singing feat will be considered for the Limca book of records -quiet a classical feat for singer-DNA MUMBAI

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- Alarinchina Girija Gaanam-SAKSHI
- Sarigamala 'Sangeetha Lakshmi'-VAARTHA
- Alarinchina gaathra kutcheri-EENADU VIZAG
- Swara Raga Girija pravaaham-ANDHRA JYOTHY

- Seshamamba sevalu spoorthy daayakam-SAAKSHI
- Seshamambaku Rotary award-EENADU MUMBAI
- 14 gantala paatu swararchana-EENADU MUMBAI
- Sarigamala nilayam kaapadali nirantharam-EENADU GUNTUR
- Eka daati ga 12 gantalu 60 keerthanalu-EENADU VASUNDHARA
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- 12 gantala paatu Thyagaraja keethanalu -EENADU RAJAHMUNDRY
- Thyagaraja keerthanalatho nagara mahila record-EENADU VIJAYAWADA
- Sumadhura Sasthreeya Sangeetha Kalakaarini DR.T.Girija Seshamamaba-SAKSHI
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